

**Supplementary Material: Application of a Thermal-Mechanical-Biological (TMB) Model to
Assess Landfill Airspace Utilization Under Seasonal Waste Placement in Cold Regions**

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Figure S4: Simulated results for Scenario S3: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature evolution at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only (biodegradation excluded); values in brackets in (c) indicate Biodegradation Ratio (BR)

Figure S5: Simulated results for Scenario S4: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature evolution at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only (biodegradation excluded); values in brackets in (c) indicate Biodegradation Ratio (BR)

Figure S6: Simulated results for Scenario S5: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature evolution at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only (biodegradation excluded); values in brackets in (c) indicate Biodegradation Ratio (BR)

Figure S7: Simulated results for Scenario R2: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature evolution at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only (biodegradation excluded); values in brackets in (c) indicate Biodegradation Ratio (BR)

Figure S8: Simulated results for Scenario R3: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature evolution at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only (biodegradation excluded); values in brackets in (c) indicate Biodegradation Ratio (BR)

Figure S9: Simulated results for Scenario R4: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature evolution at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only (biodegradation excluded); values in brackets in (c) indicate Biodegradation Ratio (BR)

Figure S10: Simulated results for Scenario R5: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature evolution at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only (biodegradation excluded); values in brackets in (c) indicate Biodegradation Ratio (BR)

Part 1. Constitutive Relationships of the TMB Model

The modulus of elasticity of the instantaneous spring and the spring in the Kelvin-Voigt body was expressed as a function of the overburden pressure according to Equation S1 and S2, respectively.

$$E = E_S + M P_{ref} \left(\frac{\sigma}{P_{ref}} \right)^N \quad \text{Equation S1}$$

$$E_{kv} = E_{Skv} + M_{kv} P_{ref} \left(\frac{\sigma}{P_{ref}} \right)^{N_{kv}} \quad \text{Equation S2}$$

where E_S and E_{Skv} are the starting moduli of elasticity in the instantaneous spring and the spring in the KV body, M , M_{kv} , N , and N_{kv} are fitting parameters, P_{ref} is a reference pressure taken as the atmospheric pressure, and σ is the applied overburden pressure.

The reduction in void spaces, which results from MSW settlement, brings the solid particles into closer proximity with one another. Therefore, the thermal conductivity of MSW is expressed as a function of its density (Equation S3).

$$\lambda = \lambda_1 + \frac{\rho - \rho_0}{\rho_f - \rho_0} (\lambda_2 - \lambda_1) \quad \text{Equation S3}$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 are the minimum and maximum values of the thermal conductivity, ρ_0 is the initial density of MSW at placement, and ρ_f is the density at the end of simulation.

Latent heat was integrated into the expression for the specific heat capacity (Equation S4). Therefore, when the temperature of MSW falls within the range of -1.6 to -0.6 °C, the specific heat capacity becomes dependent on the value of a latent heat term, which accounts for the energy required to thaw the liquid fraction of the frozen MSW and is assumed to occur over 1 °C.

$$C_p = \frac{L}{\Delta T} \text{ when } -1.6 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} < T < -0.6 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \quad \text{Equation S4}$$

where C_p is the specific heat capacity and L is a latent heat term.

Part 2. Thermal Boundary and Heat Generation Representation

Tracking heat generation rates over time (Figure S1a) presents numerical challenges when temperature is factored in, as transitioning between curves would require the model to adjust temporally to higher or lower rates (e.g., shifting from a cooler to a warmer curve). Hanson et al. (2013) proposed an alternative approach by defining heat generation rate as a function of expended energy. By incorporating this method, the model can track expended energy over time, allowing the heat generation rate to be represented as a function of both expended energy and temperature (Figure S1b).

Figure S1: Heat generation curves proposed by Hanson et al. (2013) expressed as a function of: (a) time; (b) expended energy

Ambient temperature, a key factor in determining thermal fluxes at the surface of each lift when exposed to the atmosphere, was modeled as a sinusoidal function varying between -20°C and $+30^{\circ}\text{C}$, as shown in Figure S2.

Figure S2: Sinusoidal representation of the ambient temperature

Part 3. Model Input Parameters

The input parameters used in the TMB model were employed from Alghazali et al. (2024, 2025) and are summarized in Table S1.

Table S1: TMB model input parameters

Optimized Parameter	Value	Unit
$E_S; E_{Skv}$	385; 71.7	kPa
$M; M_{kv}$	6.28; 1.92	---
$N; N_{kv}$	1.01; 1.06	---
$v; v_{kv}$	0.35; 0.34	---
τ	90.7	day
E_{DG}	0.15	---
$\lambda_1; \lambda_2$	0.426; 0.949	$W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$
$\rho_0; \rho_f$	930; 1800	$kg \cdot m^{-3}$
C_p	2.71	$kJ \cdot kg^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$
L	18.2	$kJ \cdot kg^{-1}$
v	3.0	$m \cdot s^{-1}$

Part 4. Additional Scenario Results

Figure S3: Simulated results for Scenario S2: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only; values in brackets indicate BR.

Figure S4: Simulated results for Scenario S3: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only; values in brackets indicate BR.

Figure S5: Simulated results for Scenario S4: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only; values in brackets indicate BR.

Figure S6: Simulated results for Scenario S5: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only; values in brackets indicate BR.

Figure S7: Simulated results for Scenario R2: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only; values in brackets indicate BR.

Figure S8: Simulated results for Scenario R3: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only; values in brackets indicate BR.

Figure S9: Simulated results for Scenario R4: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only; values in brackets indicate BR.

Figure S10: Simulated results for Scenario R5: (a) cumulative settlement, (b) temperature at lift centers, and (c) vertical temperature profiles at Days 1460 and 1825. Dashed lines in (a) represent mechanical settlement only; values in brackets indicate BR.

References

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